

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 4.3 2nd Annual standardisation recommendations Public

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Summary

This Deliverable D4.3 was developed in Task 4.3 and details recommendations for standardization in the field of

- Remote Desktop Protocols (RDP),
- Social Engineering, and
- Automotive Digital Forensics, which is the main focus of this Deliverable.

based on needs, experiences and expectations expressed by Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) during dedicated practitioners' workshops in the framework of CYCLOPES WP 2, Identification of practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements.

Practitioners' needs expressed in other workshops organised within WP2 such as:

- "Investigations involving Cloud Services" held on 22nd – 23rd February 2023 in Vienna, Austria, and
- "Cryptocurrency as a facilitator for Cybercrime" held on 7th – 8th December 2022 in Riga, Latvia

will be subject to the Deliverable D4.4.

Introduction

WP4 Overview

Work Package 4 is divided in the following tasks:

Task 4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference

The aim of this task is to develop WP4's Terms of Reference, defining in detail:

- The standardisation state of the art in the area of fighting cybercrime: identifying relevant CEN/CENELEC/ISO technical committees, related projects and other national and international activities. Determining the relevant stakeholders and highlighting persons in law enforcement interested in the topic (within consortium partners and the wider CYCLOPES LEA Community). Agreeing on the structure for WP4 standardisation reports.
- Innovation uptake state of the art in the security area: identification of current legal regulations, frameworks and best practices providing LEAs with an effective procurement approach for innovative solutions. Recognising the relevant stakeholders and persons in law enforcement that are interested in this topic.

Deliverable D4.1 contains WP4's Terms of Reference.

Task 4.2 Standardisation recommendations

Partners involved in this will participate in the practitioners' workshops, facilitating one-hour discussions dedicated to previous experiences related to standardisation, expectations, priorities and needs in this area. Combining information gathered from the practitioners' workshops with ongoing analyses of current and forthcoming works conducted by

standardisation bodies will be a baseline for the series of annual reports on standardisation recommendations.

Task 4.3 Annual standardisation workshops

Based on information gathered within task 4.2, CYCLOPES will choose at least one topic, which will be further elaborated during a dedicated yearly workshop. Workshops will be organised independently, or in cooperation with particular technical committees' workshops or conferences. The ambition is to promote standardisation as an effective tool in the fight against cybercrime, while exploring the opportunities to streamline processes and procedures that will maintain efficacy and maximise effectiveness. The inputs gathered from the participants during the yearly workshops will be summarized in the reports that constitute the Deliverables 4.2 to D4.6, Annual standardization recommendations.

Task 4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations

Innovation uptake is a process, starting from the elicitation of the specific needs of users, utilising the most appropriate innovation procurement model for the demand, and then ensuring the greatest impact of a new innovation – with a specific testing, validation and improvement loop. In this task, we will gather and collate existing frameworks, best practices and guidelines for innovation uptake in the Security area, along with the outcomes in WP3. Other activities in this task include the assimilation of key aspects of the materials gathered; providing recommendations for LEAs on the most congruent approach for cybercrime innovation uptake.

WP4 Objectives

WP4 has two main objectives:

- 1) to identify priorities related to fighting cybercrime which require more standardisation;
- 2) to develop recommendations, facilitating and fostering cybercrime innovation uptake in LEAs.

WP4 will contribute to the overall CYCLOPES project Objective 4:

Ob 4. To indicate priorities regarding domains requiring standardisation and innovation uptake

4.1 To define a roadmap with recommendations for standardisation based on the needs and possibilities for the standardisation of tools, procedures and trainings related to fighting cybercrime.

Related KPI: An annual report providing recommendations for standardisation will be delivered. The composition of these reports will create a standardisation roadmap.

Methods of measurement: Tasks 4.2, 4.3 and deliverables D4.2 to D4.6.

4.2 To provide a roadmap with recommendations to LEAs for the effective (also cost-efficient) innovation uptake, based on identified experiences, best practices, legal regulations and EU/national financial and organisational incentives for innovation uptake.

Related KPI: One annual report with recommendations on innovation uptake will be prepared. The innovation uptake roadmap will be a composition of all 5 reports.

Methods of measurement: Task 4.4 and deliverables D4.7 to D4.11.

WP4 Deliverables

D4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference (M06)

D4.2 1st Annual standardisation recommendations (M12)

D4.3 2nd Annual standardisation recommendations (M24)

D4.4 3rd Annual standardisation recommendations (M36)

D4.5 4th Annual standardisation recommendations (M48)

D4.6 5th Annual standardisation recommendations (M60)

D4.7 1st Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M12)

D4.8 2nd Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M24)

D4.9 3rd Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M36)

D4.10 4th Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M48)

D4.11 5th Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M60)

WP4 Partners

CYCLOPES partners participating in the individual tasks of WP4 are presented in table 1.

Table 1 CYCLOPES partners' involvement in WP4 tasks

Partner Acronym	Partner full name	T4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference	T4.2 Standardisation recommendations	T4.3 Annual standardisation workshops	T4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations
ASI	Austrian Standards International	X	X	X	
BFP	Police Federale Belge			X	X
CPEB	College of Policing Limited, United Kingdom	X	X	X	X
DITSS	Stichting Dutch Institute for Technology, Safety & Security				X
GDCOC	Glavna Direktsia Borba S Organiziranata Prestupnost			X	X
GUCI	Ministerio del Interior, Spain			X	X
HO	Home Office United Kingdom			X	X
IANUS	IANUS Consulting Ltd.				X
KWPG	Provincial Police Headquarters in Gdansk			X	X
MPF	Malta Police Force			X	X
MUP	Ministry of Interior, Croatia			X	X
NPN	The National Police of the Netherlands			X	X
PPHS	Polish Platform for Homeland Security	X	X	X	X

D4.3 2nd Annual standardisation recommendations

Partner Acronym	Partner full name	T4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference	T4.2 Standardisation recommendations	T4.3 Annual standardisation workshops	T4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations
SPA	Polismyndigheten Swedish Policy Authority	X	X	X	X
SPLV	Iekšlietu Ministrijas Valsts Policija State Police of the Ministry of Interior, Latvia			X	X
ZITIS	Zentrale Stelle für Informationstechnik im Sicherheitsbereich	X	X	X	X

1. Selected Topic: Cybercrime relating to Remote Desktop Protocols and similar technologies

On 10. and 11. February 2022 WP2, Identification of practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements, organized a workshop in the area of Cybercrime relating to Remote Desktop Protocols and similar technologies.

Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP) and related technologies became an increasing target for cybercrime – both, on staff members of organisations as well as business systems through social engineering or technical means, trying to install clients using those protocols.

Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP) is a proprietary protocol developed by Microsoft. There are no specific (open) standards but only on general level from [ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27](#), Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection, [CEN/CENELEC JTC 13](#), Cybersecurity and Data Protection, and [ETSI TC Cybersecurity](#).

Partners of Task 4.2 participated in the WP2 Workshop in the area of Cybercrime relating to Remote Desktop Protocols and similar technologies and collected the following needs expressed by practitioners. These needs were assessed regarding how these needs can be met by standardization.

- 1) Practitioners from Latvia and United Kingdom expressed the need for **training** and **awareness raising**, e.g. to prevent data loss after law enforcement take out devices.
- 2) Practitioners from Belgium, The Netherlands, Poland, Spain and United Kingdom expressed the need for **standardized protocols** for freeware and standardized communication protocols, which can be used for easy data exchange such as requesting remote information from RDP tools providers and VPN providers. It was proposed that RDP/VPN software providers have to log, implement and hand over on LEA request logfiles persevered for a longer period, specific information which can help identifying suspects and activating two-factor authentication as a default standard.
- 3) Practitioners also expressed the need for standardized procedures for **data exchanging** and **acquiring data** from abroad as well as standardized **incident reports** for international exchange.

In principle, the needs related to **training, awareness raising, data exchange and acquiring data and incident reporting** can be answered by the International Standard ISO/IEC 27035, *Information technology — Information security incident management*, with its three parts:

- [Part 1:2023](#), Principles and process

This part of the standard is the foundation of the ISO/IEC 27035 series. It presents basic concepts, principles and process with key activities of information security incident management, which provide a structured approach to preparing for, detecting, reporting, assessing, and responding to incidents, and applying lessons learned.

The guidance on the information security incident management process and its key activities given in this document are generic and intended to be applicable to all organizations, regardless of type, size or nature. Organizations can adjust the guidance according to their type, size and nature of business in relation to the information security

risk situation. This document is also applicable to external organizations providing information security incident management services.

- [Part 2:2023](#), Guidelines to plan and prepare for incident response

This part of the standard provides guidelines to plan and prepare for incident response and to learn lessons from incident response. The guidelines are based on the “plan and prepare” and “learn lessons” phases of the information security incident management phases model presented in ISO/IEC 27035-1:2023, 5.2 and 5.6.

The major points within the “plan and prepare” phase include:

- information security incident management policy and commitment of top management;
- information security policies, including those relating to risk management, updated at both organizational level and system, service and network levels;
- information security incident management plan;
- Incident Management Team (IMT) establishment;
- establishing relationships and connections with internal and external organizations;
- technical and other support (including organizational and operational support);
- information security incident management awareness briefings and training.

The “learn lessons” phase includes:

- identifying areas for improvement;
- identifying and making necessary improvements;
- Incident Response Team (IRT) evaluation.

The guidance given in this part of the standard is generic and intended to be applicable to all organizations, regardless of type, size or nature. Organizations can adjust the guidance given in this document according to their type, size and nature of business in relation to the information security risk situation. This document is also applicable to external organizations providing information security incident management services.

- [Part 3:2020](#), Guidelines for ICT incident response operations

This part gives guidelines for information security incident response in ICT security operations. This document does this by firstly covering the operational aspects in ICT security operations from a people, processes and technology perspective. It then further focuses on information security incident response in ICT security operations including information security incident detection, reporting, triage, analysis, response, containment, eradication, recovery and conclusion.

This part of the standard is based on the "Detection and reporting" phase, the "Assessment and decision" phase and the "Responses" phase of the "Information security incident management phases" model presented in ISO/IEC 27035-1.

The principles given in this document are generic and intended to be applicable to all organizations, regardless of type, size or nature. Organizations can adjust the provisions given in this document according to their type, size and nature of business in relation to the information security risk situation.

This part of the standard is also applicable to external organizations providing information security incident management services

This issue of **data exchange and acquiring data** is also addressed by CASE (Cyber-investigation Analysis Standard Expression) providing "*an extension of the Unified Cyber Ontology (UCO), which defines classes of cyber objects (e.g., items, tools, people, places), the relations to other cyber objects, provenance of items and actions taken in an action life-cycle. The CASE domain of discourse is focused on "investigation" concentrated on Observable Objects and their associated Facets, whereas the UCO serves as an ontological foundation for modeling the broader cyber-domain, treating observable cyber-items and their associated facets more generally. Developers of systems and tools used in cyber-investigations are working to export information in CASE format to allow automated normalization, combination, correlation, and validation of information, which means less time extracting and combining data, and more time analyzing information.*"

The topic of **standardized protocols** for freeware and standardized communication protocols falls in the domain of ETSI and is covered by numerous ETSI Standards such as those developed under [ETSI TC Lawful Interception](#) (LI) and [ETSI TC CYBER](#).

Since the needs expressed by practitioners during the workshop of Cybercrime relating to Remote Desktop Protocols and similar technologies can be met by existing standards based on an in-depth analysis, there is no recommendation for standardization. One observation might be that there is a general lack of awareness about the existence of these standards and this can be solved by a better engagement of standardization bodies with standards users, including LEAs.

2. Selected Topic: Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime

On 30. and 31. March 2022 WP2, Identification of practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements, organized a workshop in the area of Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime.

In the context of information security, social engineering is the psychological manipulation of people into performing actions or divulging confidential information such as PIN or passwords. There are several forms¹:

- **Blagging:** Blagging is when someone makes up a story to gain a person's interest and uses this to encourage them to give away information about themselves, or even send money.
- **Phishing:** Similar to blagging, a phishing email will ask a person to send personal details but pretends to be from a business. They can often look convincing but may contain spelling errors or URLs that do not match the business's website.
- **Pharming:** Pharming is a type of cyberattack that redirects a user from a genuine website to a fake one. The fake website will often look like the genuine one. When a person logs in, it sends their username and password to someone who will use it to access their real accounts.
- **Shouldering:** This is the simplest form of taking personal details. Shouldering is looking at someone's information over their shoulder, for example looking at someone enter their PIN in a shop or at a cashpoint.

Within these different categories, crime domains break down further with examples such as Phishing having sub groups which refer to the people targeted – such as Whaling – or the platforms used – such as Vishing(Voice calls) and Smishing(SMS).

Areas of fraud such as Business Email Compromise (BEC) and CEO Fraud remain very significant and are often a result of a system compromise and harvested information from the use of Root Kits to socially engineer the recipient.

NIST SP 800-63-3² defines Social Engineering as the act of deceiving an individual into revealing sensitive information, obtaining unauthorized access, or committing fraud by associating with the individual to gain confidence and trust.

Partners of Task 4.2 participated in the WP2 Workshop in the area of Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime and collected the following needs expressed by practitioners. These needs were assessed regarding how these needs can be met by standardization.

- 1) Practitioners from Bulgaria expressed the need for a **standardized procedure for performing an investigation**, especially when engaging with LEAs from outside the European Union.

¹ <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/znnny4j/revision/2>

² National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), "National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Special Publication (SP) 800-63-3, Digital Identity Guidelines," 2 March 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.800-63-3.pdf>.

- 2) Several practitioners expressed the need for a **standardized framework for complaint receivers**, i.e. standardised parameters when reporting complaints such as what a victim has to report, what a first responder has to collect from the victim to start the investigation (which type of cybercrime, date, transaction, etc.).
- 3) Several practitioners expressed the need for a **standardized data exchange format** between LEA's like in Fraud cases where there is the inter-agency, informal network CARIN of law enforcement and judicial practitioners in the field of asset tracing, freezing, seizure and confiscation.
- 4) There is also the more general need for a **glossary of terms** usable for technical people like first responders, prosecutors, judges, etc. which explains all sorts of terms regarding cybercrime phenomena and IT/investigation related terms such as hash values, whaling, romance scam, smishing, spear phishing, etc.

Like for the topic of Cybercrime relating to Remote Desktop Protocols and similar technologies (see Clause 1) the International Standard ISO/IEC 27035, *Information technology — Information security incident management*, with its three parts can be useful for answering the needs for a **standardized procedure for performing an investigation, standardized framework for complaint receivers** and for a **standardized data exchange format** (this implies using the CASE standard).

Regarding the need for a glossary of terms used in fighting cybercrime and digital forensics there are different standards containing terms and definitions like [CWA 17865:2022](#), *Requirements and Guidelines for a complete end-to-end mobile forensic investigation chain*, or [ASTM E2916-19e1](#), *Standard Terminology For Digital And Multimedia Evidence Examination*. Some standardization organisations host a freely available database offering access to terms and definitions specified in their standards, for example ISO with its Online Browsing Platform <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui>.

Since the needs expressed by practitioners during the workshop of Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime can be met by existing standards based on an in-depth analysis, there is no recommendation for standardization. One observation might be that there is a general lack of awareness about the existence of these standards, and this can be solved by a better engagement of standardization bodies with standards users, including LEAs.

3. Selected Topic: Automotive Digital Forensics

On 21. and 22. September 2022 WP2, Identification of practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements, organized a workshop in the area of Automotive Digital Forensics.

Vehicles are frequently involved in modern criminal activity, either as the subject of the criminal activity in the case of vehicle theft or as a facilitator for the crime, with transport surrounding a crime or being used as part of the commission of an offence such as getaway cars.

Additionally, luxury cars are a typical commodity obtained with the spoils of criminal activity. As the number of sensors and computational capacity of vehicles continues to grow, the wealth of data they collect, and share offers a significant opportunity for Law Enforcement.

Automotive digital forensics can be seen as securing/ acquiring digital data related to a vehicle that can be of relevance in a judicial investigation. It is a very broad subject that accumulates several different investigative disciplines and techniques.

Practitioners identified developing improved tools to access live vehicle data and introducing a standard for vehicle system architectures as the key priority areas for the law enforcement community.

3.1. State of the art in the selected topic

Applying the methodology specified in D4.1 for the area of Automotive Digital Forensics the following standardization committees were identified together with related standardization activities:

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, *Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection*, especially the Joint Working Group ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/JWG 6, *Cybersecurity requirements and evaluation activities for connected vehicle devices*, between ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 and ISO/TC 22/SC 32.
- CEN/CENELEC JTC 13, *Cybersecurity and Data Protection*
- ISO/TC 22/SC 32, Road vehicles, Electrical and electronic components and general system aspects, especially its Working Group ISO/TC 22/SC 32/WG 11, *Cybersecurity*
- ETSI TC Cyber, *Cybersecurity*
- ETSI TC *Lawful Interception (LI)*

The following EU policies are related to the selected topic:

- Directive 2012/13/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2012 on the right to information in criminal proceedings
- Directive 2014/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 regarding the European Investigation Order in criminal matters
- Directive (EU) 2016/343 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on the strengthening of certain aspects of the presumption of innocence and of the right to be present at the trial in criminal proceedings
- Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by

competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

3.2. Practitioners' needs

Partners of Task 4.2 participated in the WP2 Workshop in the area of Automotive Digital Forensics and collected the following needs expressed by practitioners. These needs were assessed regarding how these needs can be met by standardization.

- 1) Practitioners expressed the need for **standardisation of system architectures and vehicle data ports**, i.e. an international standard that homogenises system architectures and data ports in new vehicles to overcome barriers due to of proprietary data formats and system architectures and to realize interoperable international automotive digital evidence standards.

See Sub-Clause 3.3.1.

- 2) Practitioners expressed the need to standardize **data sets collected and stored by OEMs** (Original Equipment Manufacturers) and how the data can be made available in which format, to better understand the data.

See Sub-Clause 3.3.2.

- 3) Practitioners from expressed the need for a **Standard(s) supporting Tools to bypass encryption**. Practitioners estimated that encryption of data held on vehicles is 5 to 6 years behind encryption of mobile devices. Whilst the development of vehicle encryption is on a different trajectory to mobile devices, it is likely to become industry standard in the future representing a significant challenge to Law Enforcement. In addition, the challenge of industry patching vulnerabilities, leaves Law Enforcement in need of constant development of new exploits and tools to bypass encryption.

See Sub-Clause 3.3.3.

Considering the needs expressed by practitioners in the WP2 Workshop, assessed by T4.2 and having identified those standardization committees with which these needs can be discussed to elaborate recommendations on standardization, the following standardization committees were contacted by T4.3 Lead (ASI):

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/JWG 6, Cybersecurity requirements and evaluation activities for connected vehicle devices
- CEN/CENELEC JTC 13, Cybersecurity and Data Protection
- ISO/TC 22/SC 32, Road vehicles, Electrical and electronic components and general system aspects,
- ISO/TC 22/SC 32/WG 11, Cybersecurity

- ETSI TC Cyber, Cybersecurity
- ETSI TC Lawful Interception (LI)

Representatives from these standardization committees were invited to a standardization workshop, which were hold online on 24. January 2023, in order to:

- indicate priorities regarding domains requiring (further) standardisation
- define a roadmap with recommendations for standardisation based on the needs and possibilities for the standardisation of tools, procedures and trainings related to fighting cybercrime.

More than 25 participants joined this standardization workshop, including standardization representatives, especially the Chair of ETSI TC Lawful Interception (LI) and experts participating in ETSI TC LI c, and representatives from the following organization (including CYCLOPES partners):

- Austrian Standards International
- Belgian Federal Police
- Bundeskriminalamt Germany, including representatives participating in ETSI TC LI, and KT52-1 Car Forensic
- College of Policing, UK
- Coordinator Lawful Interception, Chair ETSI TC LI, Special Services | Telefónica Germany GmbH & Co. OHG
- Estonian Police and Border Guard Board
- Tencastle UK (expert ETSI TC LI)
- French Ministry of interior -Prefecture de Police
- Malta Police Force, Cyber Crime
- National Police Chiefs Council UK
- National Police of the Netherlands
- Polish Platform for Homeland Security
- South Wales Police
- State Police Latvia
- Swedish Police
- UK Homeoffice
- Utimaco Germany (ETSI TC LI expert)
- West Mercia Police
- ZITiS

3.3. Recommendations on standardization

3.3.1. Standardisation of system architectures and vehicle data ports

The considerable variation in vehicle system architectures represents a significant challenge for Law Enforcement. Practitioners all flagged this as a key barrier to investigations and suggested that the development of an international standard on system architectures would be extremely helpful. Likewise, a standard for data ports in new vehicles would provide a clear route for data extraction. These standards would make investigations and the development of automated tools far more straightforward.

Other issues discussed in the workshop:

- extracting, accessing and encrypting data stored in the cloud or in the network connected with other vehicles or the infrastructure (smart cities);
- ensure privacy and security, respect the law and data ownership (consent) and ensure through due process that data can be used as evidence in court case;
- focus not only on vehicle manufacturer but also on other parties such as car rental companies or car insurance companies who install features in the car, e.g. for tracking the vehicle, vehicle and driver performance or to identify which mobile phone was used to open the car.

The chair of ETSI TC LI confirmed, that this need can be addressed by ETSI TC LI. The ETSI TC LI chair recommended that LEAs and representatives from digital forensics unit should follow the process for participating directly in the work of ETSI TC LI, i.e. to become national ETSI members and then to engage in the Technical Committee with other LEAs, car manufacturers, telecommunication companies and other stakeholders for building a community which has a common understanding before starting with a “technical” standard which needs to comply with different jurisdictions.

Considering this is not only a European issue international organisations like Interpol could be invited to this standardization activity. There is a clear interest of all to have a reliable and lawful interface such as the example of VIN (Vehicle Identification Number) to SIM.

A solution might be to address this need in a to be proposed supplement to the ETSI TR 103 854, *LEA support services; Interfaces for Lawful Disclosure of vehicle-related data: scenarios, examples and recommendations*.³

The ETSI TC LI Chair informed that the next ETSI TC LI plenary meeting will be on 31. Jan. - 2. Feb 2023 and on 18.-19. April 2023 there will be a Rapporteurs meeting. For both meetings there are commitments from the automotive industry to engage with LEAs to bring this matter forward.

3.3.2. Data sets collected and stored by OEMs

Based on the discussion in the workshop participants concluded that a standardized collection and storage of data sets is very difficult to impose on OEMs (Original Equipment Manufactures). A “One size fits all” approach almost unfeasible considering the diversity and increased complexity due to how this issue evolves over time from different sources and how the data sets are built.

³ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_tr/103800_103899/103854/01.02.01_60/tr_103854v010201p.pdf

One solution might be to use standards as building blocks for such endeavour. One source might be the standards drafted under the responsibility of ISO/TC 22/SC 31, which deals with Data communication for vehicle applications including

- Data buses and protocols (including dedicated sensor communication)
- V2X communication (including V2G)
- Diagnostics
- Test protocols
- Interfaces and gateways (including those for nomadic devices)
- Data formats
- Standardized data content

ETSI could provide standards e.g. for time stamps, localisation. It is recommended to focus on certain data sets instead of a one-size-fits-all solution.

One solution might be to standardise the hand over format/interface to LEAs (data mediator).

3.3.3. Standard(s) supporting tools to bypass encryption

Based on the discussion in the workshop participants concluded a backdoor solution is not favoured in order not to be in conflict with the law and avoid jeopardizing evidence for court cases.

A stronger cooperation between LEAs/forensic laboratories and car manufacturers is recommended.

Cybersecurity by design is increasingly applied with the concept of connected vehicles. Autonomous vehicles will accelerate this challenge following increasing demands from insurance companies but also car manufacturers. So, (lawful) data sharing (in line with cybersecurity and privacy) has to be foreseen already during the design phase.

With this there is no recommendation for standardization at the time being.

3.4. List of stakeholders

In the area of Automotive Digital Forensics the following stakeholders were identified:

- National LEAs,
- Europol,
- The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS),
- EU Agency for law enforcement training (CEPOL),
- EC DG HOME,
- EC DG JUST,
- Interpol,
- Forensic laboratories,

- Forensic Tool vendors,
- Legal and ethical advisors,
- Prosecutors,
- Defence attorneys,
- Judges,
- Ministries of justice,
- Car manufacturers,
- Car rental companies,
- Car insurance companies,
- World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations as a working party of the Inland Transport Committee (ITC) of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE)

It should be noted, that CYCLOPES created a working group in the area of 'Automotive Digital Forensics' to share knowledge, experience and best practices, to exchange relevant information about tools and to learn about activities undertaken by other countries as well as to collaborate with colleagues at European level. This Group can act as an information hub to raise awareness among LEAs and related parties about specific standardization activities and as an incubator for further standardization recommendations.

4. Follow-up of and update for recommendations from previous reporting periods

Deliverable D4.2 dealt with standardization recommendation in the field of Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies. Since the needs expressed by practitioners in the CYCLOPES WP2 workshop regarding this field were adequately addressed and discussed with representatives from standardization communities and most of these needs are already met in existing standards, there is no follow-up of and update with one exception. This exception relates to the use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine-Learning in mobile/digital forensic and the potential need for standardization. Based on the forthcoming AI Act⁴ there is a standardization request of the European Commission to the European Standardization Organisation CEN and CENELEC to elaborate European Standards to support the AI Act⁵.

Conclusion

Needs expressed by practitioners in the CYCLOPES WP2 workshops regarding Remote Desktop Protocols (RDP), Social Engineering, and Automotive Digital Forensics were adequately addressed and discussed by Task 4.3. The main focus of the activities in this Task during this reporting period was laid on Automotive Digital Forensics. For this topic a standardization workshop was held with representatives from standardization communities.

Most of these needs are already met in existing standards or can be met with supplements to existing standards such as ETSI TR 103 854, *LEA support services; Interfaces for Lawful Disclosure of vehicle-related data: scenarios, examples and recommendations*. Those needs which cannot be solved by (voluntary) standards the justification is provided in this Deliverable.

As already indicated in the last Deliverable D4.2 there is a clear recommendation, that standardization organisations should put more effort in engaging with stakeholders next to those who already participate in the drafting of these standards, especially LEAs, and making them aware on the solutions provided in those standards.

Since CYCLOPES created a working group in the area of 'Automotive Digital Forensics' to share knowledge, experience and best practices this group can act as an information hub to raise awareness among LEAs and related parties about specific standardization activities and as an incubator for further standardization recommendations.

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021PC0206>

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/52376>

Annex A: Standardization overview

In ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004⁶), 1.1 standardization is defined as an activity of establishing, with regard to actual or potential problems, provisions for common and repeated use, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Important benefits of standardization are improvement of the suitability of products, processes and services for their intended purposes, prevention of barriers to trade and facilitation of technological cooperation. Standardization supports the social and economic development by ensuring safety, quality and competitiveness of products, services, and processes on various levels (e. g. performance, composition, interoperability, applicability and many more). This in turn supports economic activity of businesses of all sizes and allows them access markets all over the world.

Standardization is governed by the principles of consensus, openness, inclusiveness transparency, national commitment and coherence as outlined in the Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade of the World Trade Organisation (WTO TBT Agreement) and in Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on European standardisation.

The output of standardization are standards. According to ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, 3.1 a standard is a document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Standards are voluntary in their application and should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology, and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits. Standards are initiated and drafted by stakeholders such as industry, incl. SMEs, public authorities, research organisations, societal and environmental stakeholders, consumer organisations, trade unions and conformity assessment bodies.

There are numerous organizations developing standards, ranging from companies, consortia and industry in the private sector, to national, regional and international organizations. The latter three constitute the bulk of the international standardization system, required by the WTO TBT Agreement to follow its principles and requirements for standards development. There are also NGOs with specific socio-economic or environmental goals that develop and publish standards.

National Standardization Bodies (NSB) are standardization organizations located in each country. They bridge the local communities with groups of relevant stakeholders outside of their country and represent the pillars of the European and International standardization. Being member of European Standardization Organisations NSBs are obliged to implement European Standards as national standards and withdraw any conflicting national standards.

The European standardization activities are conducted within the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC), and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

CEN brings together the national standardization bodies of 34 European countries and provides a platform for standardization in various areas, including products, materials, services, and processes. CENELEC ensures standardisation in the electro-technical

⁶ ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, Standardization and related activities — General vocabulary, is adopted in Europe as European Standard EN 45020:2006.

engineering field, and ETSI produces standards for information and communications technology.

The network of European standardization includes more than 200.000 experts from different countries and from the different stakeholders, i. e. business, industry and commerce, service providers, consumers, environmental and societal organisations, public authorities, and regulators, as well as other public and private institutions. The European Standardization Organisations aim to support needs of the market and of different stakeholders, promoting the European Standardization System and leading the implementation of best practice in standardization around the world. They collaborate with key stakeholders' organisations at national, European and international level, support international Standardization and cooperate closely with international Standardization Organisation such as ISO and IEC. Participation in European Standardization follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of European Standards.

International standardization activities are conducted at three major international Standardization Organisation: International Organization for Standardization (ISO), International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and International Telecommunication Union (ITU).

ISO is an independent international organization that includes 165 national standards bodies as its members. International standards, produced by ISO, cover a wide variety of areas and represent consensus of experts from many countries. All CEN members are also members of ISO.

Members of IEC are 89 National Committees, represented by delegates from industry, research and government bodies of each country. IEC produces standards covering all aspects of production and use of electrical and electronic devices and systems. All CENELEC members are also members of IEC.

CEN and CENELEC have dedicated agreements with the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), promoting the benefits of the international standards to international trade and markets harmonization. The high level of convergence between the European and international standards is facilitated by the ongoing technical cooperation between CEN and ISO (Vienna Agreement) and between CENELEC and IEC (Frankfurt Agreement). The main objectives of these agreements are to provide a:

- framework for the optimal use of resources and expertise available for standardization work;
- mechanism for information exchange between international and European Standardization Organizations to increase the transparency of ongoing work at international and European levels.

International Standards from ISO and IEC following the Vienna or Frankfurt Agreement become the status of European Standards (designation EN ISO, EN ISO/IEC, EN IEC).

ITU is an inter-governmental organization belonging to the United Nations and develops technical standards that facilitate the use of public telecommunication services and systems for communications in the area of ICT. Its membership comprises nearly 200 countries and almost 800 private-sector entities and academic institutions.

Participation in International Standardization of ISO and IEC follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of International Standards.

A vast array of normative documents is classed under the generic label of "private standards". Generally, a normative document developed and published by an organization outside of the recognized standards development organizations at national, regional, or international level is considered to be a private standard. There is not only a vast range of private standards (and growing in number), but there are also significant differences between the bodies and organizations that develop these standards related to such aspects as governance, development approach, stakeholder engagement, transparency, and consensus.

Some of these Private Standards Development Organisations liaise with recognized standards development organizations. Such examples are IEEE and ENISA liaising with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection or OASIS liaising with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 2, Biometric technical interfaces. Some specifications from Private Standards Development Organisations were provided by them to recognized standards development organizations to be implemented as standards.

Another aspect to consider is how standardization bodies deal with intellectual property in standards. In many sectors of the economy, companies make significant financial and human investments in the development of new technologies and products. As a result, the best available technology that experts want to include in a standard is often protected by one or more patents. This is especially true in certain areas where interoperable and complex technologies cause standard developers to consider new and emerging technologies that are normally protected by patents. These contributions may contain patented technologies which are commonly known as Standard Essential Patents (SEP). When it is not possible on technical grounds to make or operate equipment or methods which comply with a standard without infringing a SEP, i. e. without using technologies that are covered by one or more patents, the patent is described as being 'essential' for the application of the standard. To preserve the universal approach of standards, while also respecting the rights of the patent holders, ISO, IEC, ITU, CEN, CENELEC and ETSI have developed an intellectual property rights (IPR) policy. In brief, this policy encourages the early disclosure and identification of patents that may relate to standards under development. The IPR Policy provides for the incorporation of patented technology into new standards, on condition that the IPR holder is ready to allow this either without financial compensation or at Fair, Reasonable and non-Discriminatory (FRAND) conditions to other standard users.

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